

Advantages and Disadvantages of the free market in Afghanistan

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Abstract

This research seeks to get the benefits and deficiencies of the free market in Afghanistan, and firstly, to identify concepts; views on the free market and the evolution of the free market, and examines the dimensions of the free market, such as its advantages and disadvantages. Then, descriptive research method and quantitative method were used and distributed questionnaires on this subject. This study analyzes the content of the study in two dimensions: the dimension of the free market pros and cons, and then examines the free market process of Afghan society. The statistical population of this study is the Ministry of Commerce and Ministry of Economy staff in Kabul city, which according to the Morgan table 124 people were selected as the sample population and the questionnaire was distributed. To get answers, the Likert method was used which yielded interesting results in this study. The results of this study, from the viewpoint of the two ministries, show that the high return on capital, the relevance of the market supply and demand, the improvement of the lives of capable people, the creation of a competitive environment in the environment, the attraction of foreign investment, the compilation of government bureaucracy costs, the variety of products In the market, the motivation of individuals to earn more money and economic growth and development is one of the benefits of a free market in the country. One of the deficiencies in the free market in the country can be stated: the greater classification between the capitalist and the exotic; the increase of individualism in society; the lack of real understanding of the free market in the country; the increase in economic inequality in society; the creation of a difficult environment in the country And more wealth distribution to specific people. After receiving the results of this study, the researcher put forward suggestions for improving and generalizing the free market in the community.

Keywords: Free Market Afghanistan

Problem Statement

The free market is a decentralized system , under which economic processes, resource allocation, the production and consumption of goods and services, and the distribution of income and wealth, under the mechanism of prices as the regulator of the market mechanism, are made by free decisions of all agents and economic activists, both producers and consumers, Under an institutional framework that is determined and guided by the state through which the conditions of justice and freedom are established and guaranteed (Arzoo, 1389, p. 53).

The free market in the country has its own advantages and disadvantages, the disadvantage of this kind of system is that each person has the right to sell any kind of goods at any price. In this case, some poor families justify a lot of problems.

The important thing is that the market mechanism is never an unconstrained Mechanism; the market system is shaped and expanded under a defined institutional framework. In fact, this institutional framework supports, steers, and monitors the market system as a system that determines the processes of resource allocation, the production, and consumption of goods and services, and the distribution of income and wealth. Meanwhile, the government as a sovereign plays a fundamental role in the formulation and regulation of market rules and structures and is recognized as the guarantor of the executive, supervisor and market leader. The key issue here is that the efficiency and stability of the institutional framework that supports the market system determine to a very decisive extent the efficiency and stability of the market system (Yusufzai, 2000, p. 45).

Importance and Significance of research

As we all know, the market is of great importance in any society, especially in developing countries, and it plays a vital role in the continuation and livelihoods of the citizens of each country in systems that have become

increasingly popular in the world recently. Free has a greater role than other systems, in Afghanistan after the formation of the government in 2002 and the establishment of the constitution of the free market system in the country. The significance of this discussion is that so that the people of the society and the economic sectors become aware of the importance of free markets and their shortcomings, I, therefore, urged myself to do research in this regard, on the one hand, I have a duty to do this during these days. I have been doing it and served a different container for the market and the economy.

Research purposes

The main objective

- Identifying the benefits of a free market in the country.

Sub-objectives

- Awareness of free market systems.
- Awareness of the state of free markets in some countries.

Research questions

A. The main question

- What are the advantages and disadvantages of the free market in the country?

B. Sub questions

- What are the market systems?
- What is the government's supervision of the market system?
- What is the free market in the country?

Hypotheses

The main hypothesis

- It is assumed that the important benefits of the free market system are to sell Gisen at the price and price of the seller, and its biggest defect is the inability to buy for the poor, who cannot afford the material he needs in a free market system.

Hypotheses

- It seems that the free market has the right to sell its property at any price it wants to sell, regardless of the criteria of the state and its peers, and this is one of the advantages, and to make all the capital of the country available to several people It's one of the biggest free market flaws.
- It is assumed that buying and selling objects and assets at market prices is called the free market.
- The government seems to be the regulator in every part of the country. In the same way, it will have a high degree of market surveillance. If the market system is closed, the government will even set the price for the commodity, and it will only have regulatory aspects in the free market. It is assumed that the free market, in addition to deficits in developing countries, also benefits.

Background Research

One of the books in this area, the crime of adultery, is a book called "The Market Systems," by George Maxwell. In this book, the system of the market has been introduced and presented a variety of systems, each of which outlines its advantages and disadvantages, including the free market system, how the system is and how it should be deployed to this system. That use will take place.

Another book on marketing and marketing has been published by Mohammad Baqer walidi, who was published in 2004. The book focuses on marketing, but one section of the market-specific market system, in particular the free market, states that the free market system is more widely promoted in third world countries or poorer countries, and each one has a stake in each The price that it wants to sell is one of the weaknesses that keep the country from progressing, and the people of these countries cannot have any better capital at all, and all the capital of the country is in the hands of several special people.

Key Research Concepts

Market. The network and the place that establishes the relationship between the buyer and the seller (Pour Moghayem, 1395, p. 47).

Free Market. The free market is a system that is free of charge, and at any cost, it can sell goods and objects (Pour Moghayem, 1395, p. 53).

Advantages. Benefits are derived from the word advantage, which means benefits or benefits.

Defects. Defects of the headline are defective and include all the losses that result from an object (Yusufzai, 2000, p. 45).

Literature Review

Rothbard's theory of free market system

Rothbard writes, some market criticisms argue that ownership rights are contradictory to human rights. But these criticisms forget that in the free market, every individual owns his or her own workforce and can refrain from accepting any contract to provide its services in this system. On the other hand, all rights and even property rights are part of human rights, and the market never neglects human rights.

Rothbard refers to a general charge against the free market, which is that this system governs the forest law in society so that it "feeds dogs, dogs" and this system strikes human competition for competition, and on the other hand, material successes in this system contradict spiritual, spiritual and philosophical values. But we all know that forest is a society full of coercion, threats, and harassment. A forest is a society that lowers the quality of life and its standards. While healthy market competition between producers and suppliers is a completely peaceful process that everyone benefits from, and as a result of this profit, the standard of living of everyone goes up. Undoubtedly, as a result of the material success of societies with a free market, public wealth increases and allows people to enjoy a higher level of satisfaction than other societies.

Milton Friedman's Theory

Economic freedom for political freedom is a necessity. If the people can co-operate without coercion or central direction, the field of political power will be reduced. "Friedman, Milton and Rose Friedman, free to choose a personal paper, studies conducted by the Canadian Free Market Support Fraser Institute; The Harriet Foundation, a supporter of the US Open Market and the Wall Street Journalists, has a relationship between economic freedom and political and civil liberties (to a degree that Friedrich von Hayek claims to be). They also agree with Hayek on the point that countries that restrict economic freedom ultimately restrict civil and political freedoms.

Refers to a set of potential and actual buyers of a product or service. Historically, the market is referred to as a place where buyers and sellers refer to the exchange of goods or services. But economists call the market for buyers and sellers who buy and sell certain goods or services. From a marketing perspective, the buyer sets the market. At the same time, the word market is sometimes referred to collections other than customers or buyers, such as the labor market or the marketplace.

Free market definition

The market is one of the most important concepts in economics, and as human beings hear the word of the market, at first glance, it is a commodity market and something like that, the market is referred to as the economic concept of exchange. Generally, it can be defined as such. (Masoud, 1380, pp. 591-519). The marketplace is the place where buyers and sellers freely meet and trade (the best measure of market demand means a clear understanding of the market situation (Lal Bhagavati, 2005, p. 150). The division of markets is the existence of In which the type of goods or production factors in which the supply and demand are offered is the criterion of division (Moshbaki, 1383, pp. 37-39). The market is the area in which it deals with the purchase and sale of goods or services and resources, for each individual Or there is a market service in which the behavior of suppliers and customers is mutually exclusive (Babaei, 1380, p. 37; Golehi, 1367, pp. 253-254).

Types of markets

We have already discussed and analyzed the concept of the market in the economy, and we said what market segmentation is. One of the important market segments according to the number of participants is the number of applicants and supply. The market will be realized if, on the one hand, the market is at least one person (supplier and applicant), this kind of market is called the exclusive market (buying and selling). Another type of market is the multipolar market that markets Multi-polar sales are famous. In this multi-polar market, several supplier companies have been placed against a large number of applicants. There are many suppliers and marketers on both sides of the market. In this case, this type of market is considered a free market. In addition to the free market, the monopoly market and the monopolistic market of markets have a large number of markets and markets that we intensively share with each other. We argue that in the economy of a society, and especially in human life, plays a major role, for example, markets, labor market, market capital, market capitalism, common market, currency market, planned and focused market, market, commodity market, The social market, etc., that all of these markets are for ease of exchange. It means that all people in a society can solve their problems by the markets and at least benefit from the markets, which, on the one hand, will bring about the welfare of the community and, on the other hand, will trigger the level of the economy of the country (Robert Evans, 2004). , Pp. 166-170).

Market economy

Market economy or market economy is a system in which the production and distribution of goods and services are carried out through a free market mechanism driven by a free-price system (rather than market-oriented ones). The main feature of this economic system is that investment decisions, or the allocation of basic goods, are initially carried out through capital and economic markets. This system is placed in the context of the economics of Planned Economics, in which investment and production decisions, as part of an integrated production program, are governed by the political system or another political body that controls production factors. , Is taken (Babaei, 1380, p. 39). In the economic model of a free market, there is no interference from the state or another source. In the capitalist societies where the theoretical model of a largely free market economy does not occur, the underground economy replaces a real free market economy (Nunezhad, 2004, p. 39; Mohtasham, 2002, pp. 201-221).

In order for an economy to be considered as a real free market, labor, goods, services, and capital must be excluded from the scope of state constraints and trade barriers, so that they can freely cross borders (Nunezhad, 2004, p. 37) 39).

A free market in Afghanistan

Afghanistan, almost after three decades of conflict, finally came into existence with the establishment of the Transitional Islamic State of Afghanistan, in which a new constitution was signed in the Constituent Election Jirga of Kabul in the twelve-twelfth chapter of 1382 and the 162 articles unanimously approved by the head of the Transitional Authority of Afghanistan. The free market economy is exemplified by the economic movements of investments and contracts, the first and the tenths of this new constitution, as follows. "The government guarantees the investments and private sector subsidies on the economy of the market in accordance with the provisions of the law, its encouragement, support, and security."

Free Market Characteristics

The similarity of goods and manufacturing units in a particular industry in the free market is quite similar, so that the purchase of this or that unit of production is indifferent to the consumer, since the similar products are not purchased, no more than the price that other sellers. Gans are required to pay a special production unit (Robert Evans, 2004, pp. 166-170).

Transparency of the market in the free market is transparent, i.e., buyers and sellers can well consider the characteristics of the market. Their information is from the full market and can predict their spending and income (Babaei, 2001, p. 45; 1382, pp. 132- 135).

The majority of business transactions are based on social or private communication, familial or social, history and ideology, and as other area research suggests that communication networks regulate business flows, business credit, information provision and participation in economic risks. Throughout the country, the largest businessmen have established financial and personal relationships with powerful people at the national, regional or local levels, which are important for both sides. For example, security, tax exemptions for contracting for a trader and preparing the ground for investing capable of abusing and consolidating political and military powers are among the benefits that power holders benefit from. Often, these high power sources Primary such as water and agricultural land are also fully controlled. Due to the bitter incidents that have been created against the economic markets, the same category can be claimed that the country's economic markets are not active, transparent and free (Massoud, 1380, p. 591; Nunezhad, 2004, pp. 37-39).

Savings and savings are some of the most important economic factors that can play an effective role in financing or the funds required for different sectors of the economy. Today, with the monetary policy of the economy, as a result of the separation of savers from investors, it is necessary for investors to transfer money and money from people who have a surplus, to those who are in short supply.

Financial Markets include stock markets and bonds markets and financial intermediaries such as banks, insurance institutions and open-hearth banks as the main components of the financial system, the task of transferring the amount from individuals who are surplus or addicted to those who are facing shortages or deficits They will be In this section, after studying how to transfer the savings to borrowers, the nature of financial institutions is analyzed first and foremost, we study here summarily and summarily financial markets (Jankhani & Parsayan, 2002, p. P. 11).

As traders profit by buying more goods and selling goods at higher prices, banks will benefit savers by giving them loans at a higher rate than interest rates. Since the bourgeois trade stopped, money brokered, banks were created and intermediaries between savers and those who had a deduction and needing money. Nowadays, banks have penetrated during economic life, or because the sector It is important to supply money in the form of current savings, so banks play a significant role in the economy, which provides for the development of trade and social progress, although Tayyek lent only commercial and short-term lending businesses a century ago, but Today, hundreds of millions of dollars were credited to the government and consumer organizations, and Bella There were various services provided by banks and financial institutions that they are creating, although in the old days there were people or institutions that borrowed money, banks are almost the most recent economic institutions in this field. Banking, which has expanded since the seventeenth century, has contributed significantly to the development of the industry. The growth of commerce in the course of the term, and if it is borrowed with money, it will generate profits that part of the profit would be passed on to borrowers (Faraji, 2003, pp. 66-67).

If trading on the stock market flourishes, this will show optimism and will show the development of future activities, and vice versa, in the case of a downturn in these bonds, the lack of confidence in the future and the change in the economic situation will indicate that the share of companies in the stock exchange The basis of financial, commercial, and good corporate governance is made by the board of directors (Tafazoli, 2004, p. 34).

Market conditions

Market conditions review The first section of the market target plan, and the institution's backbone will be presented. Marketing planners should provide the following information.

Market description - Here it is marketed, which includes various market segments. Planning the size of its market segments over the last few years to the Afghan or the unit of product, it outlines the needs plan for customers and influences the buying power of customers.

Product Survey - Here is the product sales plan, price, and gross profit statement.

Competition - Here, the main competitors' plans in their strategy are to highlight the quality of the product, distribution system, and sales promotion programs. Also, the market share of the product and the product is displayed on the other.

Distribution - Here is the plan for the distribution of recent distribution development.

Market control - Since there may be unplanned marketing plans for unforeseen events, then voluntary control is necessary (Samimi, 1373, p. 74).

Financial markets

Financial transactions are carried out both in the primary and secondary financial markets, in the initial financial market of the securities that are being released. But in the secondary financial markets of securities previously purchased in the primary markets, secondary financial markets are important for the primary financial market in terms of the exchange and censorship of primary securities. The primary task is to swap government debt securities, corporate bonds, and corporate equity securities. Bhddrkx bonds will be released soon, increasing the supply of credit. The issuance of shares and bonds in the primary securities market is backed up by the guaranteed bankers by the investor's bankers who act as brokers and brokers in secondary financial markets.

The financial markets, through the financial institutions that they have, have been gathering enough to reach the people who need to borrow, each month analyzing the money and capital markets individually (Faraji, 2003, pp. 118- 136) .

The money market is a market in which banks and some financial intermediaries, in particular, the Treasury, pay bonds to finance the financial needs of their income and expense (Askari, 2002, p. 491).

Analytical Model

Methodology

Methodology

In selecting the type of research, the researcher should specify which method and method to choose. To be precise, easy and quick to help answer research hypotheses and questions. For this purpose, a quantitative method was chosen by the researcher through a preliminary study. One of the features of the survey approach is its flexibility and multi-purpose. Surveying research in terms of low cost and the amount of data that is collected. There are scores that are comparable to the collected data, analysis for modeling and drawing scientific models. This research is a kind of quantitative study that can be testable and generalizable.

Research type

In this research, analytical and descriptive methods have been used that first gather information from books and interviews with people, and then it was expressed in an analytical and descriptive way. An analytical and descriptive method is a method that self-researcher combines with previous research and the results that the researcher himself has used in his research, then analyzes and proves his hypothesis, and seeks to achieve the goal. The researcher This method can, by using the ideas of previous researchers and its own results and the comparison between the two, be able to reach the intended destination.

Research Methodology

In the present study, the field method has been used a little, and the first category information is available by distributing the available questionnaire. In this research, a quantitative and survey approach is designed and a tool for measuring the variables of the questionnaire. A questionnaire is one of the most common and commonly used tools for gathering information in survey research.

Statistical population

The statistical population of the survey is all employees and personnel of the ministries of economics and commerce, which is about 500 people, as well as economic experts who have knowledge about information market systems.

Sample population

A total of 500 employees of the trade and economy ministries working in these two ministries, and experts on this subject, 124 people were interviewed randomly at each academic and academic level on the Morgan table, according to the Morgan table, or has requested a paper entry.

data gathering tools

In this research, the first tool of the questionnaire has been used, and second-hand tools such as articles and journals as well as books have been used in this regard. In this research, a probabilistic and randomized method is used.

Analysis method

The purpose of the research is to answer the initial question. Therefore, the researcher formulates the hypotheses and conducts the observations required by the hypotheses; then they must see that the information collected corresponds to the hypotheses, or, in other words, the observed results correspond to the results that the hypotheses expect. To understand this, we need to analyze how data is analyzed. Data analysis involves multiple operations, but three of them are comprised of a total of passes. First, describe, prepare and describe the data necessary to test the hypotheses, Then, the analysis of the relationships between variables and, finally, the comparison of the observed results with the results Expected by the hypotheses.

Analysis and analysis of the findings of this research are also classified in the first step. I used descriptive statistics such as mean, median, facial, deviation, and variance for describing it. In the second step, inferential statistics such as regression test, one-way analysis of variance and averages or t test were used to analyze the relationships between variables. Finally, a comparison was made between the results obtained and the results that the hypotheses demanded.

This research was carried out using descriptive variables derived from the questionnaire used to analyze the program (Excel). The questions in this questionnaire are based on the variables that have been identified after theoretical and exploratory studies and with regard to the facts of the statistical society. Most of the questions in the questionnaire are in the form of closed questions, with a sequential scale in the form of a Likert scale. On a sequential scale, the variables are sorted according to their severity and weakness to an attribute. This questionnaire is coded after the Percy home, and its code is included in the program (Excel) and evaluated and analyzed.

Research limitations:

- 1- Failure to carry out previous research in this regard, so that in this research, I will be inspired by the method, materials and other ways that have been done in previous research.
- 2- The lack of sufficient raw materials to investigate the extent of the research to a large extent was a major challenge for this.
- 3- The research was another challenge not to supply the materials and figures needed for research by government officials and bodies.
- 4- Since this research was conducted for the first time on the side of my servant, ignoring the correct methods and methods of research was another serious challenge to this research.
- 5- The lack of time opportunity was another challenge to this study. Because the research calls for more time and requires time to address all the dangers of this research.
- 6- The remoteness of our place of life from the ministries and departments that are involved in this study has been one of the major constraints in this research.
- 7- The lack of standard libraries and books that were used properly and correctly could be a limitation to other research and sources.
- 8- The contradiction between the statistics and the figures in some cases that confronts the researcher in two ways is another challenge to this research.

Findings of the Research

Data analysis was done in Excel, and according to the responses of the population, a questionnaire was obtained.

Gender Diagram (1-4)

According to the above model, the number of respondents who responded to this questionnaire. There are 124 people, 84 of whom are men, representing 68% of the total population, and 40 of them women, representing 32% of the total population.

Age chart (2-4) related to age

According to the chart above, the number of respondents between the ages of 18-25 zero - between ages 26-35 are 51% - between the ages, 36-45 are 26% - between the ages of 46-55 are 17%, and over the age of 60, It is 5%.

According to the chart above, the number of respondents answering this questionnaire is 61% of them from the bachelor's degree 29% of them are a master with 3% of them have fourteen passes , 3% of them have twelve passes and 4% of them were doctors the total population.

Job Schedule (4-4)

According to the above chart , respondents who responded to the questions consisted of 124 peoples, representing 67% Govt employees 16% of them privet sectors and 17% of them are NGO employees.

Diagram (5-4) Are people satisfied with the market system in Afghanistan?

In the country, which is the same free market system, they are satisfied with 92% of the respondents. Divers in this question have chosen an average option that is as good as the people, but not much satisfied with the status quo. Not to mention that about 8% of the respondents chose the option. No people are dissatisfied with the current state.

Chart (4.6) the government's lack of work in the economic arena has caused people to face a lot of problems, such as immigration and economic problems.

According to the above, about 72 of respondents fully agree with the problems that people face today, such as immigration, which is responsible for that government. The remaining 23 of the respondents agreed that the government failed in economic affairs, but 5 of the respondents answered that they did not comment on this, but 19 answered that they disagreed. The government has fundamentally grounded on economic activity, and 5 have been completely opposed to this opinion. The high level of this process is not certain that it would reduce corruption in the Ministry of Finance because it believes corruption is a widespread problem in the world and cannot easily be reduced by the Ministry of Finance. In my opinion, such people are unrelieved of the government and its instruments, which is the same e-government in Afghanistan, especially in the Ministry of Finance, which has reduced administrative corruption in the most important ministries of the country, thus increasing the transparency and trust of the people towards the government.

Chart (7-4) Are traders in the country satisfied with the free market?

As in the figure above, the percentage shows that nearly 74 percent of the Ministry of Finance employees believe that the Ministry of Finance, especially the Department of the Custom , which is known as ASICODA, has been officially created by the Ministry of Finance, most of this effective system has increased revenue in the Ministry of Finance, such as affairs and procedures Customs, such as export, import, transit, tariff control, tax collection, and all conventional and developmental expenditures have been funded by the AFMICE system and others, which will increase the national income of Afghanistan through the Ministry of Finance. 16% of those employees said that the increase in revenues from the Ministry of Finance is another reason. As the increase in taxes, the increase in imports through tax-paying customs is indicative of a depreciation rate, in the past decade, import statistics are rising from exports to a very worrisome state.

Chart (8-4) How Much Money Does Your Business Take

According to the figure above, about 9% of the respondents answered that the free market system is in favor of traders, and this percentage of respondents has chosen a very large choice, while 56% of the people who responded to our questionnaire have responded. It has chosen the highest percentage, which is the benefit of the free market for the benefit of traders in the country. But 26% of the respondents responded to the question, which is not so good for traders and has chosen the low option. While 31% of the respondents chose a very small option, 2% of the respondents chose the option at no point, which does not make sense.

Chart (9.4). The government views its interest in the free market more than anything else. Therefore, it is more in favor of a free market system.

If we look well in the form above, then notice that there are two opposing views in this chart. One has chosen a great deal while a large number of others have chosen a very small option. In this chart, 9% of the people said that they are very much The free market is in the interest of the government, and for this reason the government wants to implement this system, while 46% of the people agree that 7% of the people do not comment on this and 32% of the people oppose this relationship and 6% Other people have completely disagreed with this opinion.

Chart (10.4) how successful has the government pursued the free market System

As seen in the figure above, about 96% of people agree with this view. Approximately 70% of people strongly agree that the free market has been at the ease of the people and people have been able to ease their needs. got. While 20% of the people agreed, 4% of the population did not have a particular opinion, while 2% of the people disagreed with this view, and 4% of the public were opposed to this opinion.

Diagram (11.4) How much of our fellow citizens in the free market system can nourish their needs well?

According to the statistics obtained from the above figure, the free market system in the country is very satisfied. 31% of the respondents answered that it is very effective and people can easily achieve their needs as much as 44%. Of the respondents who responded that they are very effective, they choose 7 percent of the low-budget option, while 14 percent said it was very low-impact, and 4 percent said it was not effective at all, and people could not easily access their goods on the market. Free is easy to get.

Chart (12. 4) It seems that the benefits of the free market system are more than necessary, more attention is paid to this, and both the people and the government want it.

According to the above graph, the most respondents answered that yes the benefit of the free market system is higher than its losses. And I fully agree with it, while 35% of respondents agree. 9% of respondents did not comment on this, 24% opposed this view, and about 9% of respondents completely disagreed.

Chart (13. 4) what is the impact of the free market system on the economy of the country?

The information collected through the questionnaire in the chart above shows that out of a total of 124 people, 101 of them (81%) of the total population, believed that in the current state of the country, the free market is very effective and the reason Why it is effective, they say that there is a direct relationship between the buyer and the seller, who can find and buy the buyer of the necessary item, and on the other hand the seller can sell it at his own expense. And the rest of the 23 people, representing 19% of the total population, believe that a free market system is effective in the country's economy, but not so much because it increases purchasing power for capitalists and equals the purchasing power of the poorest people. brings.

Chart (14. 4) what is the economic growth of a country depends on market systems?

In the chart above, the collected data states that of a total of 124 people, 115 of them were of the opinion that the country's economic growth and development are related to market systems and that the market system is very effective in the country's economic development. And in different conditions, the macroeconomic situation influences the country's economic growth. And 56 of them confirmed the high option, while 9of them had the option of moderate, and the rest of them believed that the market system had little effect on the country's economic growth and development.

Graphic diagram (15-4) How much people can use the free market system in their daily lives?

According to the above form, all the people who provided their views on the above question, which constitute (100%) of the entire population, believed that people made their lives in line with the market system and their lives could well go well.

Chart (16. 4) what is the free market system for foreign imports?

On the chart above, the aggregate information obtained shows that all respondents who comprise 124 individuals representing 100% of the total votes believed that the free market system would increase domestic production and exported foreign imports He takes up a lot in the country.

Chart (17. 4) what is the free market system contributing to domestic production?

The above table shows that the number of respondents who expressed their opinion on the above question. A total of 124 respondents, 76 people, believed that the free market system had a huge impact on domestic production and made domestic products Widespread. While 37 were high, 11 were average.

Graphic (18-4) Does the government interfere in balancing prices in the market system? If so, which way?

The above figure shows that the information gathered from a total of 124 people indicates that 116 of them question the question of whether the government interferes in balancing prices in the market system. If so, which way? The positive point is that the government intervenes to balancing the intervention and how much it answers, which monitors the price by controlling and sending the board to the shops and markets. And only two respondents expressed their opposition to the above question.

Graphic Schedule (29-4) Are people satisfied with the free market system in the country?

The contents of the above figure make it clear that the question asked by a total of 124 people, 112 of them (90%) of the total population, believe that yes, people are, to a degree, satisfied with the state of the market systems in the country, and according to this system and the conditions of their life, And it is consistent. The remaining eight, which make up a small percentage, are opposed to this.

Scheme of the Month (20-4) does the free market system in the country meet the needs of people in the country?

The chart above explicitly states that all respondents, totally 124, believe that yes, the free market is in the best interest of the man and meets the needs of the people in the country, and especially in the city of Kabul.

Graphics sheet (21-4) has the free market system led to investment by foreign companies inside Afghanistan?

The chart above shows that the response from respondents, of whom 124 are 97%, agree that yes, the free market system in the country has made the foreign investment because foreign investors are accustomed to the free market conditions, and It has a belt head and invests in overseas. Only 27% respondents disagree.

Graphic Design (22-4) has the free market increased domestic and foreign trade?

The chart above explicitly states that all respondents, of a total of 124 people, believe that yes since everything in the market is freely available to the seller and the buyer, this can increase internal and external exchanges.

The Market Scheme (23-4) has contributed to the free market system in domestic production

The above table shows the total of 124 people who expressed their views on the above question, of which 56 were fully agreed that the free market system contributes to domestic production and increases domestic revenues. 52 of them agreed, 16 of them though.

Market Scheme (4-24) Market systems are controlled by the government.

On the graph above, it is seen that 124 of them, who expressed their views on the above question, totally agree with this idea, 70 , 32 of them agree, 18 of them did not comment, 4 of them disagree with this opinion.

Plot Market (25-4) The free market system in the country to the capital of the country will be placed by several capitalists and businessmen of the country, and other people in the community live in poverty.

The above model states that the information obtained through this questionnaire shows that out of a total of 124 people, 56 of them believe that the problem with the free market system in the country has created to hold the capital of the whole country in the hands of several people. Is. 56 of them have chosen a great deal, 8 of them are moderate, and 4 of them are low.

Graphic diagram (4-26) the free market system increases the class conflict and is more in favor of the seller than the buyer

The chart above makes it clear that 68 of those who responded to the questionnaire believed that the free market system would increase the degree of class differentiation and that those who were not able to buy more than before would increase their differences of opinion . And 44 of them appear to be happy with the courts, while 8 of them are moderate and 4 respondents are not well-informed.

Market Scheme (4-27) the free market system has made it easier for the seller and buyer to trade.

In the chart above, the information from a collection of 124 people suggests that 48 of them fully agree that this system will increase the convenience of business between the buyer and the seller, 68 of them agree that in some cases they will increase the problems. Because in some cases, because the price of objects is not constant, it causes problems in some cases. 8 of them have no idea.

Chart (2. 4) the 4th-4th figure of the free market has led to an increase in domestic production in the country. And competes with foreign imports

The above-mentioned chart is a representation of Ukraine, out of a total of 124, 64 of them totally agree. The free market system makes it possible for people to contribute to the production of goods and goods and to increase their quality and increase their foreign imports. , 56 of them agree that it can boost domestic production and the 4 of them Do not comment . The free trade system, one in its opposition, cannot result in the growth of domestic production.

Conclusion

It follows from the following chart that the advantages of a free market in the country are greater than its deficiencies if it is properly implemented in the country, it can be in the interests of our people and our country, and as a result, our country is making significant progress. To achieve

Pros and cons of the free market in Afghanistan

The deficiencies of the free market system in the country	Advantages of the free market system in the country
1. The investment priorities are towards investing in areas that are more profitable, rather than	1-The flow of capital and assets in this economic system is the one that has the highest rate of return on investment, and as a result, over time, the total turnover of capital in the economy grows, and

<p>investing in sectors that have the greatest benefits for society or the greatest demand for them in society.</p> <p>2. Under these economic conditions, the workspace becomes harder, and people can work in a society that has more skills, higher education, and more abilities. These people earn a lot of money and earn a small salary against other people. As a result, the gap in economic space increases.</p> <p>3. The increase in economic and social inequalities is another disadvantage. In this space, the rich grow fast, and the poor do not have the power to grow at high speed, which makes their distance higher every day.</p> <p>4. Although the characteristics of free economics are ideal and guide the economy towards growth, it is very difficult to create this ideal economic climate. For this reason, many economists suggest a mixed economic system in the country. A system in which governments engage in the allocation of economic resources and wealth distribution, but individuals and businesses are busy with activities in the economic space and economic decision-making.</p>	<p>the economy then develops and reaches its maximum potential. This system will increase the opportunity for economic growth, which will then pave the way for the development of the economy and the rise in the value of the gross domestic product.</p> <p>2-In this system, supply and demand are closely interrelated. A person who has a good idea or produces a good product can quickly supply this new idea or product to the consumer market, and subsequently, the product is exposed to the use of people who are potential consumers. On the other hand, when a particular commodity is demanded by people - there are plenty of people who can massively make the product - there is no doubt about entering the capital into this area and earning profit from the place where the production line was created and invested in it Does not exist.</p> <p>3-In a market economy, a person with the ability and perseverance can quickly create a better life because in such an economic environment, the conversion of a lot of work, perseverance , and effort to physical capital and material wealth is easier ,and the speed of wealthy people with ideas New is much more than other economic systems.</p> <p>4-Competition among different enterprises to maximize the efficiency of economic activity is high, and industrial and industrial units do nothing to reduce costs and increase the efficiency of economic activity.</p> <p>5-In such an economic environment, there is a greater incentive to create creative methods of production, since all firms are thinking of producing new goods in low-cost ways.</p> <p>6-In this economic environment, there is a more foreign investment because of the opportunity for economic growth and profitability, and the economic and commercial interaction of this country with the outside world is greater because it has more and more innovative products for supply.</p> <p>7-The size, power , and cost of government bureaucracy in this economic system are less because different activities in the closed and state-owned economies are the responsibility of the state to the private sector and the power of the state bureaucracy has been weakened.</p> <p>8-Different types of goods and services are offered in the market , and each person can buy and consume according to their taste.</p> <p>9-The incentive to earn more money and raise the standard of living in these countries will make more people quickly acquire technical and social skills that can help them get the job market more quickly.</p>
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As a result, we can say that an open market economy is one of the best and most ideal systems in the world. A system in which all economic decisions are made by the actors of different markets and the interaction between individuals and enterprises in the society is determined by how the goods and resources are allocated to the economy. In this system, people decide on how to invest and use different commodities, and in fact, these people are the key to all economic activities and economic success.

The market economy has seven very important characteristics. Including that people buy the goods and services they are applying for and have enough money to buy. So, in this system, money is introduced as an essential element of life. In this economic system, provision of social needs is less important than making an economic profit, and since everyone is trying to maximize income, it is understood that the rich and the poor live in a situation.

The free market has led to the growth and development of various sectors in the country. A free market is a place for employment in our beloved country. In different sectors, it has made it possible to work efficiently and effectively in the capacity building of the labor fanatics.

It is a fact that the free market has rapidly accelerated the telecommunication system in the country, which is really unique in the history of the country, and we are well aware of all aspects of the development of this field.

Recommendations

1. For the implementation of the free economic system, security in the country is considered essential and the government will make a serious effort in this regard.
2. Because the government guarantees the rights of all individuals, institutions, organs, the necessity of a transparent judicial system is a fundamental condition of the free market, in order to ensure the rights of all aspects of society, while a transparent and convincing judicial system There is no part in the country.
3. The government, as a guarantor of the rights of all individuals in the country, should have serious control over the activities of the private sector and, in proportion to their benefits and income, make the nationalities.
4. The government should be in the current situation. High Raw Materials. Technological The goods and goods that are effective in the country's economic growth and development are less taxed or tax-exempt.
5. Mines, natural reserves, and forests, including public resources. Because the free market operates on the basis of more benefits. So the resources mentioned should be extracted, regulated and conserved by the government. And the above resources should not be left to the private sector because the state apparatus is currently unable to accurately determine the volume, value, and cost of these resources.
6. It is the central duty of the state to reconstruct and establish the country's economic structures. You should not expect this from a free market.
7. The free market is the system used by Western and rich countries in the world. Accordingly, countries that want to use this type of system must know all its advantages and disadvantages and have a rational decision in this regard. Examine the systems of other countries.
8. Media about economic systems for people. So that the people of Akane and Fahmida decide on the fate and the active systems of the market.
9. The state should determine the course of the movement of a free market economy based on religion and religion, customs, traditions and sanctities of the community.
10. The people and the government both seek to expand and maintain a new free market system. Because this system has more advantages than the closed system, which is priced by the government. In this system, the buyer and seller will understand their needs before and after.

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